

Application of Organic Chemical Spectroscopic Techniques to Study the Organic Chemical Structure of Coal in Solid State and in Solubilised (Extract) Form

D. K. SHARMA

Centre for Energy Studies, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi-110 016

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With the ultimate depletion of oil, dependence on coal for the oil supplies will increase. No real breakthrough in developing the cheaper and convenient coal conversion technologies can be made without clearly understanding the organic chemical structure of coal. Most of the spectroscopic and chromatographic techniques developed to work on solutions can not be applied on coal as it is relatively insoluble in generally available solvents. Spectroscopic techniques, such as FTIR, solid state ^{13}C nmr, esr and mass spectroscopy can be applied on solid coal. Solubilisation (extractability) of coal in generally available organic solvents (such as chloroform) can be enhanced through depolymerisation (phenolation), reduction, alkaline degradation and acetylation of coal. Solubilisation of coal through these reactions affords the application of spectral techniques. Studies have been reported on Assam coal. Pyrolysis and hydro-pyrolysis of Godavari coal yield predominantly aliphatic and aromatic tars, respectively. Spectral studies of coal tars reveal some information on the organic chemical structure of coal. A combination of spectroscopic studies of coal extracts and coal tars obtained would help in the studies of the organic chemical structure of coal macromolecules.

COAL is an organic rock which is embedded with inorganic mineral matter. Though, coal is too dirty to convert, still this organic macromolecule has been liquefied to get oil and gasified to get gaseous fuels during Second World War. The oil crisis of the seventies, intensified research in the area of coal conversion again. With the ready availability of oil now which is expected to continue in 1980s and with relatively stable oil prices, the research in the area of coal research has been diluted. Nevertheless, the fundamental truth remains that the limited oil reserves are not going to last for more than 30–50 years. The situation is more alarming for countries like India, which has meagre oil reserves. Oil reserves in India are expected to last for not more than ten years at the present rate of consumption. But India has huge coal reserves, which are expected to last for more than 100–200 years. Research is being extended^{1,2} towards characterising Indian coals using latest analytical and computer techniques, which would help in better understanding the detailed mechanisms of coal conversion, e.g. solvolytic extraction/refining, pyrolysis, direct liquefaction and gasification. Ways are being found to better utilise coal liquids. Coals are being chemically processed to get clean fuel to solve the environmental issues related with coal.

The most intricate problem confronting the chemists is the physical and organic chemical structure of coal. Since coal is insoluble in the generally available organic solvents, so most of the latest spectroscopic techniques can not be used on coal.

Major advances in this direction have been made in the application of FT-ir spectra, high resolution solid state nmr spectral technique to study the structure of coal. FT-ir spectroscopy is the only analytical technique which works best on coal. But ir spectral studies are limited only to the functional group analysis of organic molecules. Thus, it is possible to get some idea about functional group and class analysis of Indian coals using this technique.

Figs. 1 and 2 show the FT-ir spectrum of Assam coal and Neyveli lignite. Numerous studies have been reported on the ir spectral analysis of various coals and coal extracts and assignments of functional groups to different ir spectral absorptions have been identified³⁻⁶. Table 1 shows the assignments to the FT-ir spectral absorptions for Assam coal and Neyveli lignite. In coals, there is a predominant absorption at 1600 cm^{-1} which has been assigned to the condensed polycyclic aromatic rings and $-\text{C}(\text{OH})=\text{C}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$ structures. Aromatic rings also show CH stretching vibrations at 3030 cm^{-1} , and the absorptions in the range $700-900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ invariably represent the adjacent H-atoms in an aromatic ring. Absorptions at $1400-1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ also represent aromatic functionalities. The strong absorptions at $1440-1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are in part due to CH_2 groups, but the contribution may originate from CH_2 groups, aromatic C=O bonds and strongly bonded OH groups. A contribution may arise due to cyclic structures of hydroaromatic

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectrum of original Assam coal.

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectrum of original Neyveli lignite.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF COAL

	Assam coal	Godavari coal	Neyveli lignite
Proximate analysis (% dry basis)			
Moisture	1.5	4.1	8.7
Ash	8.3	10.1	6.1
Volatile matter	42.0	38.6	46.6
Fixed carbon	48.2	42.9	38.6
Ultimate analysis (% dry ash free basis)			
Carbon	77.04	79.00	62.04
Hydrogen	5.69	4.94	5.81
Nitrogen	1.49	1.81	0.98
Sulphur	3.75	1.14	1.40
Oxygen (by difference)	12.08	12.70	30.27

rings. Absorptions at 1 250, 1 091, 1 031 and 1 010 cm^{-1} are due to etheric groups. Distinct peaks at 1 091, 1 031, 1 010, 938, 913, 537–540 and 470 cm^{-1} are ascribed in Kaolinite (mineral matter of coal) due to Si–O stretching vibrations. A wide band at 1 163, 1 116, 1 090 and 980 cm^{-1} can be attributed to iron and cadmium sulphates present in coal mineral matter.

The ^{13}C nmr spectra of solid coal sample of Godavari coal showed two broad peaks, one in the aromatic region (greater one) and the other in the aliphatic region (smaller one). These spectra do not yield any substantial information, excepting that these can be utilised for calculating the degree of aromaticity of solid coal samples. The aromaticity of Godavari coal was found to be 76%. X-Ray crystallography is another technique which can be used for the analysis of solid coal samples^{6–8}. This helps in studying the three dimensional aromatic and hydroaromatic network of coal structure. It has been found that the structure of coal is different from that of diamond and graphite. Other studies which can be carried out on the solid coal samples are the esr studies⁹. The esr studies of coal have revealed that coal contains high concentrations of free radicals ($> 0.02 M$). The radicals detected in coal system are mostly inert. The unreactive neutral radicals in coal are prevented from abstracting H-atoms by complete shielding of the radical centre. It could also be possible that certain types of radicals, such as phenalenylic radicals possess large amounts of resonance stabilisation energy to render them inert. Highly stable radical ions also account for a large fraction of the observed esr signals in coal systems. Mass spectral study is another technique which could be applied to solid coal sample, but it has its own limitations since coal is relatively nonvolatile upto 250°, and above 350° it starts devolatilising and pyrolysing resulting in complex tar molecules through various cracking and crosslinking reactions. The mass spectrum of solid Assam coal showed peaks at *m/e* 91, 153, 251 and 495. Since it is known that bituminous coals have molecular weights in the range 2000–5000, the mass spectral studies on coal can not be much informative as coal is less volatile. Assam coal was

depolymerised (phenolated) using *p*-toluene sulphonic acid in phenol^{10–12}. Mass spectrum of the benzene/methanol extract (in solid form) obtained from the depolymerised coal showed peaks at *m/e* 368, 276, 274 and 200 in decreasing intensity, showing the degradation of Assam coal through depolymerisation. Depolymerised coal was further subjected to degradation using aqueous alcoholic NaOH solution. Mass spectrum of the degraded depolymerised coal did not show any peak beyond *m/e* 270, showing further degradation of coal. Depolymerised coal was also reduced using Li in ethylenediamine. Reduced depolymerised coal (benzene/methanol extract) also did not show any peak beyond *m/e* 270. These studies showed that chemical degradation of coal was a promising technique for studies of organic chemical structure of coal. Further studies in this direction are in progress.

Scanning electron microscopy reveals the information about the physical state of the coal, and which is beyond the scope of discussion as it relates to the porosity and physical structure of coals. Barring SEM, the above mentioned techniques are the only spectral techniques which can be used for the studies of organic chemical structure of coal. Attempts have been made to solubilise the coal, so that the studies could be made using high resolution nmr spectral techniques. But the solubility of coal in generally available solvents is very poor. Table 1 shows the analysis of Assam coal. Table 2 shows the extractability of Assam coal in generally available solvents.

TABLE 2—SOLVENT EXTRACTION OF ASSAM COAL IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Solvent	Extractability (% dry ash free basis)
Benzene	4
Chloroform	9
Tetralin	15
Decalin	14
Anthracene oil	20
Creosote oil	6
Tetrahydrofuran	8
Carbon disulphide	2
Phenol	5
Nitrobenzene	2
Monoethanolamine	35
Ethylenediamine	44
Pyridine	12
Quinoline	15
Butanol	4
Ethanol	1

This was found to be maximum in ethylenediamine (EDA). Chloroform extract of Assam coal was made free of solvents. The solid extract was dissolved in CDCl_3 and its ^1H nmr spectrum was recorded. Table 3 shows the ^1H nmr spectral results of the chloroform extract of original Assam coal, acetylated Assam coal, depolymerised (phenolated) Assam coal, acetylated depolymerised (phenolated) Assam coal, depolymerised-reduced Assam coal and reduced-depolymerised Assam coal. Chloroform extract of the original coal was found

TABLE 3—¹H nmr SPECTRAL (CDCl₃) DATA OF COAL* EXTRACTS WITH TMS AS AN INTERNAL STANDARD (PROTON RATIO)

δ ppm	Proton type	CHCl ₃ extract of OAC	Acetylated coal using Py-Ac ₂ O	Acetylated DP coal	DP-Red Coal A	Red-DP Coal A	DP Coal
>8.0	Hydrogenbonded	—	0.86	—	—	—	—
8.7-8.3	Triaromatics	—	2.37	—	—	—	—
8.3-7.7	Phenolic hydroxyl	—	1.29	2.04	2.19	—	11.89
7.7-6.2	Monoaromatic and diaromatic	—	14.01	88.13	45.38	41.48	61.07
5.8-4.3	Olefinic-H next to ring	—	0.86	0.77	7.56	7.20	—
4.3-3.4	Ring joining methylene	—	1.51	1.02	1.37	1.75	2.23
3.4-3.2	Acetylenic	—	—	—	—	—	—
3.2-2.4	Methin, methylene-α	16.99	—	3.32	2.19	—	1.36
2.4-2.0	Methyl-α/acetyl	4.04	10.35	15.08	2.19	1.75	17.10
2.0-1.4	Methylene-β/acetyl	11.25	12.50	10.49	12.05	6.99	—
1.4-1.0	Methyl-β	48.18	43.1	15.71	13.54	22.58	5.45
1.0-0.6	Aliphatic-α	19.54	13.15	13.44	13.53	17.25	—

*OAC=Original Assam coal, Py-Ac₂O=pyridine-acetic anhydride, DP=depolymerised (phenolated) coal, Red-DP=reduced-depolymerised coal, DP-Red=depolymerised-reduced coal.

to contain only aliphatic compounds as the resonance signals in the aromatic region were absent. Acetylation of coal, using acetic anhydride in pyridine, resulted in the extraction of aromatic products from coal. This was very encouraging study, as acetylation enhanced the chloroform extractability of the original coal from 3 to 10%. Protons due to acetyl CH₃ appeared at δ 1.5-2.4. About 14% proportion of protons appeared in the aromatic region of the ¹H nmr spectrum of acetylated coal as against 0% in that of the original coal. ¹H nmr spectrum of depolymerised coal showed 52.78% protons in the aromatic region, 2.21% in the ring joining methylenes, about 25% in the aliphatic region and 20% in the phenolic hydroxyl region (due to phenolation of coal).

Reduction of the depolymerised coal using Li in EDA was carried out¹⁰⁻¹². ¹H nmr spectrum of reduced depolymerised coal showed that the proportion of aliphatic protons increased up to 51.32%, and protons due to phenolic hydroxyl being absent. In another study, the Assam coal was reduced using Li in EDA and this reduced coal was subjected to depolymerisation using *p*-toulensulphonic acid in phenol. ¹H nmr spectrum of depolymerised-reduced coal showed the presence of 2% protons due to phenolic hydroxyls and about 45% in the aromatic region. Aromaticity of the phenolated-reduced coal was more than that of the reduced-phenolated coal. In another attempt, the depolymerised coal was acetylated using acetic anhydride in pyridine. This enhanced that extractability of depolymerised coal in chloroform, from 25 to 35%. ¹H nmr spectrum of the acetylated depolymerised coal showed lesser aromatic character than that of the depolymerised coal. Reduction in phenolic hydroxyls was obvious because of the acetylation. Acetyl protons (25%) appeared in δ 1.5-2.4 region in the ¹H nmr spectrum. The only other interesting feature of the spectrum was the reduction in the ring joining methylene groups, which showed slight degradation

of the depolymerised coal as a result of acetylation. These studies clearly showed that depolymerisation (phenolation), acetylation and reduction are very interesting reactions for studying the organic chemical structure of coal. Further studies on the ¹³C nmr spectrum of the derivatised coals are in progress.

The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra of tar obtained from the pyrolysis of Godavari coal using different atmospheres at temperature (450 to 650°), have shown that the tar contains invariably the aromatic compounds along with 10-24% of C₁₅-C₂₁ straight chain alkanes¹³. The aromaticity of the original Godavari coal was found to be 76%. This showed that 24% of carbons in the coal are present in the aliphatic form. Considering the yields of tar from coal, which was in the 30-48% range, it could be said that about 3-10% carbons of original coal have resulted in the form of straight chain aliphatic compounds in the tar. The formation of these compounds can be explained from the opening up of hydroaromatic structures of coal during heating and formation of free radicals. The side chains of aromatic ring clusters are also cleaved through thermal degradations. These aliphatic side chains combine with open aliphatic chains formed from the hydroaromatic structures. Similarly, the aromaticity of tar was found to be in the 30-45% range. This showed that the tar obtained from the pyrolysis of coal was predominantly aliphatic. The aromatic compounds of original coal follow condensation reaction pathways and form coke. Coke is predominantly aromatic containing mostly polycyclic (condensed) aromatic rings. In fact, in the inert gas and steam atmospheres, most of the aliphatic components from coal are devolatilised to form tar. Aromatic compounds present in the solid coal undergo condensation reactions on release of the aliphatic and hydroaromatic connecting links present in the coal, and form coke. In actual practice, coal undergoes degradations on heating

due to thermal instability of various connecting links joining the aromatic ring clusters together. This leads to the formation of aromatic, hydroaromatic, paraffinic and olefinic free radicals. Aliphatic and hydroaromatic free radicals combine to form tar, whereas most of the aromatic radicals reunite to form coke. When pyrolysis was carried out in the hydrogen atmosphere under 66 atm pressure^{1,8}, the tar obtained was predominantly aromatic. The aromaticity of tar was found to be 57% as revealed by the ¹³C nmr spectral studies. There was a reduction in the quaternary carbons, phenolic carbons, straight chain paraffins and also the number average chain length of the paraffinic compounds was reduced to C_{1.5}. This showed that in pyrolysis of coal, it gets thermally degraded to produce aromatic radicals. In case of hydrolysis these radicals are stabilised to give 57% aromatic compounds in the tar. These studies point towards the predominant aromatic character of coal structure, which is thermally less stable than graphite and diamond.

Juentgen explained the mechanism of pyrolysis and hydrolysis of coal¹⁴ on the basis of the organic chemical structural model suggested by Heredy and Wender¹⁵. In fact, the organic chemical structure of coal is even more complex than that of lignin and is still not very clearly understood. Studies of the coal extracts obtained through derivatisation of coal under milder conditions would help in understanding the organic chemical structure of coal more clearly. These studies can be supplemented with the studies on the tars obtained from the thermal degradation (pyrolysis or hydrolysis) of coal. The use of most modern analytical and chromatographic techniques are expected to be of great help in these studies. Further studies on the organic chemical structure of coal through derivatisation and thermal degradation and by using modern analytical and chromatographic techniques are in progress.

Experimental

The chemicals used in the present work were commercially available analytical grade reagents.

The coal samples were crushed to 60-120 BSS mesh size. Neyveli lignite was crushed to 120 BSS mesh size. The coal samples were dried in an oven at 105°.

Depolymerisation (phenolation) of coal: To Assam coal (6 g), catalyst *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (PTS; 4.5 g) in phenol (120 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed with stirring for 24 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and phenol was removed from the product by repeated steam distillations. PTS was removed by washing with hot water. The resulting depolymerised coal was dried in oven at 105°.

Acetylation: Assam coal/depolymerised coal (6 g) was added to the mixture of acetic anhydride

(30 ml) and pyridine (30 ml). The reaction mixture was shaken well and refluxed for 3 h and left overnight. The mixture was then poured in a beaker containing ice. The acetylated coal product was precipitated and filtered. The product was dried and stored in a vacuum desiccator.

Alkali degradation: A mixture of Assam coal/depolymerised coal (6 g) and 1.5% aqueous NaOH solution (100 ml) was refluxed for 24 h and cooled. The reaction product was neutralised with 2% aqueous HCl. The product was recovered by filtration and dried.

Reduction: To Assam coal/depolymerised coal (12 g), was added ethylenediamine (300 ml) and the reaction mixture was continuously stirred at 100+5°. Lithium metal (10 g) was then added to the reaction mixture in portion for 4-5 h at 100+5°. The reaction was allowed to proceed for further 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured over ice. The product was recovered after acidification by centrifugation. The reduced product obtained was washed with water and dried in oven at 105°.

Pyrolysis and hydrolysis procedures for the coal have been described in details along with the ¹³C nmr spectral details of tar in the earlier report¹⁴. FTIR spectra (KBr) of coal and lignite samples were recorded using a Nicolet 5 DX FT-IR spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) of coal samples were recorded using TMS as internal standard on a Varian (60 MHz) spectrometer.

Mass spectra of benzene/methanol extracts of the coal samples were recorded using a JEOL, JMS-D-300 compact double beam focussing high sensitivity GCMS system instrument.

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